

Keynote Address

Including learner diversity in large class teaching - Using Universal Design for Learning to sustain a systematic proactive reflection on social justice and accessibility

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Abstract

Large class teaching is seen by many practitioners and scholars as a context increasingly privileged by the neoliberal academy for revenue reasons. It is, however, a landscape often also seen as challenging in matters of inclusion and accessibility because the sheer size of the class hinders many inclusive strategies. The session will debunk two specific myths perpetuated within this landscape and explore the pertinence of UDL in sustaining a systematic, proactive and design focused approach to social justice in large class teaching. The paper first argues that Equity, Diversity and Inclusion (EDI), as an objective within higher education, is achieved through inclusive pedagogical design in the large classroom, more effectively than through mere policy. Second, the article suggests that UDL is in fact more urgently required in the large classroom than in other teaching spaces. The paper uses auto-ethnography as a method to explore the author's experiences, as a manager in disability service provision, supporting and advising instructors exploring UDL implementation in large classes.

Keywords:) EDI, UDL, teaching and learning, large classes, neo-liberal landscape, higher education

1. Context

Large classes are increasingly appealing in higher education (HE) in a business model that now systematically uses neoliberal criteria of optimal revenue, profitability and financial sustainability as prime objectives for quality assurance and strategic development (Minz, 2021). These large classes, however, also give rise to specific pedagogical challenges, particularly in relation to inclusion and accessibility (Sanger, 2020). As a result, although equity, diversity and inclusion are becoming central concerns for post-secondary campuses, these priorities can appear difficult to address and achieve in classes where the large student intake is the primary focus (Fortes & Tchanchane, 2010). This has meant that, while a considerable body of literature now exists around inclusive design in teaching and learning and more specifically around universal design for learning (UDL) (Burgstahler, 2015; Dalton et al., 2019), much of it tends to be dismissed by large classroom practitioners as impracticable or unrealistic (Kennette & Wilson, 2019; Novak & Bracken, 2019). Instead, EDI becomes, in these spaces, a matter of policy only – a conceptual concern with very little tangible implications in terms of pedagogy.

The article uses auto-ethnography (Pithouse-Morgan & Naicker, 2021) to document and analyze the author's experiences supporting and advising instructors teaching in large classes, while he was employed – for a period of four years from 2011 to 2015, as manager of an accessibility services unit on a large Canadian campus. He complements these observations with further opportunities he had to support instructors as a program head and faculty mentor, at later stages of his career. The paper debunks two common myths perpetuated in HE and suggests that, despite appearances, (i) EDI in large classrooms is best achieved through inclusive pedagogical design, and (ii) UDL is highly pertinent, pressingly needed, and perfectly achievable in large classroom settings.

2. Literature Synopsis

2.1. Social Justice in a Neoliberal Landscape

While EDI concerns are currently at the forefront of post-secondary institutions' concerns as a result of powerful wider societal movement such as the #MeToo movement, Black Lives Matters, and Truth and Reconciliation (Wolbring & Lillywhite, 2021), the discourse on social justice is often put into parenthesis when revenue, financial sustainability and growth in admissions are seen as priority (al Shaibah, 2014). The COVID crisis has threatened further the financial stability of many HE institutions – particularly as a result of low international admissions over this period - and made these priorities felt even more harshly (Purcell & Lumbreras, 2021). EDI within large classroom settings is seen as challenging as it is presumed the inclusion of diverse learners requires individual attention

and personalized assistance from instructors, something which large classroom lecturers are often not in a position to offer (González-Castellano et al., 2021).

2.2. EDI in Large Classrooms

EDI take prominence in the branding discourse of post-secondary institutions at present, but priority is also given to large class teaching as a mode of growing revenue and achieving financial sustainability (Hutt et al., 2010). It is in this context frequently assumed that EDI strategies are impossible to translate into classroom practices, and that teaching and learning should focus instead on the effective management of large student intake (Maringe & Sing, 2014). EDI is relinquished, in such a landscape, to efforts around policy and administrative mindset. As a result, instructors often feel that EDI is a matter for student services and student affairs personnel and that it has more to do with campus culture than with pedagogy (Tamik & Guenter, 2019). There is little scholarship around EDI embedded pedagogy. Assessment in large classrooms seems particularly challenging in this respect. While there is an understanding that traditional summative assessment usually encountered in the large classroom is unsuitable to address learner diversity, few alternatives are envisaged within the time and resource constraints that exist in such contexts (Glazer, 2014).

2.3 UDL in Large Class Contexts

There has been considerable growth in the momentum for UDL implementation in HE, over the last decade, both in North America and Europe (Black et al., 2015; Fovet, 2021). Exploration of UDL has spread beyond the Humanities faculties – the original disciplines within which most early adoption was witnessed - and UDL is now actively implemented through the full spectrum of subject areas (Nieminen & Pesonen, 2020; Fovet, 2021b). It is also explored both in undergraduate and graduate education settings (Fovet, 2020), and is increasingly popular in the college landscape (Boothe, et al., 2018). There is still currently, however, resistance when it comes to discussing UDL implementation in large classroom contexts in HE, even among the most eloquent of UDL advocates. Specific scholars have tackled this topic and demonstrated that the UDL model is just as pertinent to the large classroom format (Faculty Center for Teaching and e-Learning, 2012; Dean, Lee-Post & Hapke, 2017), but these practitioners and researchers are few and far between. There is currently a need to debunk some of the fears, misunderstandings, and myths being perpetuated (Farrell, 2021; Fovet, in print), as they are currently dissuading instructors from considering UDL when they teach in large class contexts.

3. Assertions

This short paper makes use of auto-ethnography to examine the myths which are often perpetuated in HE in relation to EDI, large classes and UDL adoption. The author analyzes the support work and advice he was regularly asked to provide to instructors teaching large classes.

3.1. First Myth: EDI is Best Addressed in Large Classrooms through Policy

There is considerable momentum currently in HE in relation to EDI (Dewidar et al, 2022). This very ediatized focus is the result of recent powerful societal trends that have brought to the forefront issues of social justice: Black Lives Matter, the #MeToo movement, Truth and Reconciliation/ Indigenization, Decolonizing the Curriculum, as well as the claims and protests of the Trans community and sexual minorities, have all dynamized the EDI discourse and demonstrated the urgency for change in HE. While this pressure is authentic and heartfelt, in the post-secondary sector this discourse focuses mostly on campus climate, policy, and services. EDI efforts on HE campuses ironically, as a result, avoid actually discussing pedagogy or diversity in teaching. EDI policies offer instructors very little tangible and immediately pertinent advice and support on how to diversify their pedagogy to address the full spectrum of learner diversity. This is frustrating for faculty who feel the pressure for change but remain unsupported in this process. It is also irritating for diverse students who see diversity increasingly used as a marketing feature but observe few efforts occurring on campuses to transform and update pedagogy view a view to fully addressing learner diversity. All stakeholders are increasingly seeking a model or a framework that might support this process of pedagogical change and UDL will fill this gap and serve this purpose, regardless of class size.

3.2. Second Myth: UDL is Challenging to Implement in Large Classes

Even among UDL advocates and implementers in HE, there has been some hesitation when it comes to implementing and using UDL in large class contexts. As has become apparent in the literature review, the logic of the inclusive design process is often put on hold by instructors who feel that large classes present exceptional characteristics that prevent the genuine implementation of the UDL principles. It is often assumed that the work around inclusive design does not lend itself well to a reflection on practice, when the rhythm is fast and the demands on the instructor are vast, due to large class size.

My own experiences supporting instructors, both as an accessibility specialist and as a faculty mentor, lead me to believe that the use of UDL is actually even more pressing, pertinent, and effective in large classes. I have at times witnessed first year undergraduate courses being run with 1,200 participants. At this stage, there is in fact no longer even a

pretence that the traditional lecture format is anything else than a fiction. There are often not even enough seats available for students, many have little choice but to watch the class from large screens outside the auditorium, or online from home.

This is a scenario where simple UDL design tips seeking to offer multiple means of representation become essential tools: securing systematic microphone use, having the lecturer available onscreen to improve visual accessibility, recording classes and making them available online, providing the lecture material ahead of the class, etc. A similar reflection is required in relation to offering multiple means of action and expression, when the class size becomes significant: if the lecturer no longer has the opportunity to entertain a personalized connection with the learner, traditional exam and summative assessment tools used on a large scale, for example, become meaningless. Using UDL to create more meaningful ways for students to demonstrate skills and competencies becomes necessary and even urgent. UDL will also be useful for instructors realizing the limitations of their traditional assumptions around learner engagement; the UDL principles will support them as they design more flexible methods for learner engagement to be authentically demonstrated despite – or perhaps simply because of - large class sizes.

4. And Then Came COVID

The COVID pandemic has had an impact on teaching and learning practices within HE that is still difficult to gauge with precision. It is clear, however, that it has vastly accelerated the growth of UDL and inclusive design with the post-secondary sector. First, the majority of faculty have now acknowledged and embraced their role as designers of the learning experience. It has been impossible for instructors to shy away from this realization during the pandemic simply because each of their instructional choices, during the online pivot, has demonstrated the immediate negative impact of bad design on the learner experience. In this sense, HE instructors have never been as receptive to UDL as they are now.

The second exceptional occurrence which took place during the COVID crisis is that most courses temporarily took on the characteristics of the ‘large class’ during the online pivot: most instructors had to negotiate with lack of personal contact with learners, overwhelming online correspondence, a very fast pace, and a lack of support from campus services. To some extent all classes became ‘large classes’ in the lived experiences of strained and overwhelmed instructors shifting to online instructions. Navigating the idiosyncrasies of challenging large class formats became the reality of most faculty. This has created an opportunity to advocate for UDL within these challenging experiences.

5. Outcomes

The impact of this reflection is considerable as many campuses have so far adopted an approach which leads them to focus UDL experimentation on small classes and pilot projects of limited scale. This analysis suggests that the strategy is counter-productive when, in fact, the most significant impact of UDL may be immediately noticeable in large class contexts.

5.1. Reformatting the UDL Discourse and Existing UDL Professional Development

Very few resources on UDL are available to instructors teaching large classes. Professional development (PD) is currently also lacking and there is therefore very little modelling of best practices taking place or showcasing of successful initiatives. This paper is therefore a call for action to participants in this conference to develop PD opportunities for colleagues, within which they will grow momentum around UDL implementation in large classrooms.

5.2. Developing a UDL Scholarship that is Specifically about Large Classroom Implementation

As was stressed in the review of the literature, there is currently very little scholarship focused on this topic and this is extremely counter productive, as most HE instructors will require evidence and data before they experiment with a model of instruction. It is therefore urgent for UDL advocates and practitioners to not only ensure UDL is being used in large class contexts, but to also record their experiences and initiatives, and publish accounts of their efforts so that it may develop a relevant scholarship that will support others in embarking on this inclusive design reflection within the large lecture.

5.3. Considering the Large Class Impact of UDL Adoption in Relation to the Full Spectrum of Diverse Learners

It is important to stretch the UDL discourse and reflection beyond simply a concern related to access and disability. The spectrum of learner diversity is increasingly wide, and includes – beyond students with disabilities – first generation students, non-traditional students, lifelong learners, culturally diverse students, second language learners, sexual and gender minorities, Indigenous students, etc. The percentage of learners who experiences barriers in access to learning can often therefore exceed fifty per cent of the class, when all these categories of learners are considered together; in large class contexts, this represents vast amounts of learners. The inherent demographics of these large lectures mean that inclusion needs to be a priority; solutions must be systematic and effective. UDL serves as a reliable framework to support instructor reflection daily around diversity as a broad concept (Kennette & Wilson, 2019).

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